

Protonation Constants of Salicylic and Substituted Salicylic Acids

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THE protonation constants of a few substituted salicylic acids have been reported earlier¹⁻³. No

The values of pH at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and $\bar{n}_A=1.5$ correspond to the values of pK_2 and pK_1 respectively. Refined values of pK were also obtained by point-wise calculations and linear plot method and are also recorded in Table-1.

The pK_1 value is found to follow the order: SA>SSA>5-NH₂SA>5-CISA>3-NO₂SA>3:5-DNSA in agreement with the inductive effect of the substituents⁶

The results indicate the failure of Hemmett's equation⁶⁻¹⁰.

TABLE-1 pK VALUES FOR SALICYLIC AND SUBSTITUTED SALICYLIC ACIDS

Ligand (Acid)	Half intergal method			Linear plot method			Point-wise calculation average				Average	
	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3
SA	3.15	11.80	-	3.13	11.64	-	3.33	11.76	-	3.20	11.73	-
SSA	1.94*	3.10	-	1.93*	3.07	11.71	1.98*	3.08	11.70	1.95*	3.08	11.70
5-NH ₂ SA	2.80	5.45†	-	2.80	5.43†	10.99	2.72	5.45*	10.96	2.77	5.44†	10.98
5-CISA	2.57	11.63	-	2.62	11.46	-	2.68	11.56	-	2.62	11.55	-
3-NO ₂ SA	2.30	10.35	-	2.35	10.33	-	2.25	10.35	-	2.30	10.34	-
5-NO ₂ SA	2.25	10.79	-	2.25	10.72	-	2.28	10.75	-	2.26	10.75	-
3:5-DNSA	2.08	8.13	-	2.03	8.18	-	2.01	8.21	-	2.04	8.17	-

*for SO₃H and †for NH₃⁺ (the conjugate acid)

attempt seems to have been made to determine the same in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium. The pK values of Salicylic (SA), 5-Sulpho-salicylic (SSA), 5-Amino-salicylic (5-NH₂SA), 5-Chlorosalicylic (5-CISA), 3-Nitro-salicylic (3-NO₂SA), 5-Nitro-salicylic (5-NO₂SA), and 3:5 Di-nitro-salicylic (3:5-DNSA) acids have, therefore, been determined employing Bjerrum's titration technique as reported by Irving and Rossotti⁴. Refined values are then obtained by point-wise calculation and linear plot methods and are reported here.

Experimental :

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. AR grade.

Polymetron model CL-41 pH -meter was used for pH -metric titrations conducted at 30°. Measurements were made with an accuracy of ± 0.05 pH units and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order.

pH -metric titrations of the solutions of (i) free HClO₄ and (ii) free HClO₄+Ligand (acid) were performed in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Results

The Irving-Rossotti⁴ expression was used for the calculation of $\bar{n}_A$ values. These in turn were employed for the determination of stepwise dissociation constants of the various salicylic acids used in the present investigation.

The values of pK were calculated by half-integral method making use of formation curves.

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A new Synthesis of 3-Hydroxy-3':4'-Methylenedioxy-Flavone

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IN our investigations on the flavonoids of the indigenous plants, 3-hydroxy-3':4'-methylenedioxy-flavone(II) was needed for comparison. While Hattori¹ prepared it by acid hydrolysis of the oximino derivative of the corresponding flavanone, we herein report an elegant synthesis of the flavonol (II) by the application of Algar Flynn Oyamada (AFO)reaction.